

Task Mapping in a Regularity-based Resource Partitioning Hierarchical Real-Time System

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Abstract—Virtualization via a Hierarchical Real-Time System (HiRTS) is gaining popularity in recent years. This paper introduces a Centralized Task-Partition Architecture to connect the two levels of an HiRTS whose resource level adopts the Regularity-based Resource Partition (RRP) Model. Based on this architecture, we propose two models. The Regular-Partition Periodic Task Mapping (RPM) Model aims at mapping periodic tasks to regular partitions online. The Regular-Partition Compositional Task Mapping (RCM), on the contrary, considers the mapping of both periodic and sporadic tasks to regular partitions. As the first attempt to map tasks to partitions based on RRP model, this paper presents how RPM and RCM are modeled with ideas from online Multiple Knapsack Problem (MKP). Thus, this paper completes the full picture of a RRP-based HiRTS.

I. INTRODUCTION

Virtualization is being increasingly applied in embedded systems as it can enhance the reliability [1], improve flexibility [2] and handle thermal exposures of MultiProcessor System-on-Chip (MPSoC) at the architecture level [3]. In a two-level Hierarchical Real Time System (HiRTS) [4], there are two levels: the resource level and the task level. This paper proposes an architecture and two models for connecting the resource and task levels while maintaining the transparency between them to enhance the flexibility of the model. This paper adopts Regularity-based Resource Partition (RRP) Model in the resource level. Since RRP model has been decently studied these years[5, 6, 7], the specifically designed bridge between the task and resource levels introduced in this paper, shall complete the whole picture of the RRP-based HiRTS.

A few models have been proposed for the resource level: the Periodic Model [8], the Bounded-Delay Model [9], the Explicit Deadline Periodic (EDP) Model [10] and the Regularity-based Resource Partition (RRP) Model [5]. Amongst all the aforementioned models, RRP can utilize the resources with less deviation between the ideal and the actual resource allocation [7]. Hence, this paper adopts RRP for the resource level.

The RRP Model divides physical resources into different **partitions**. As shown in the example in Fig. 1, a Virtual Machine (VM) may contain multiple partitions, e.g., VM1 contains partitions 1 and 2 [2]. Besides, a task on a certain VM is mapped only to a partition contained by this VM, e.g., Task 1 and 2 are mapped to Partition 1. Several studies have been

Fig. 1. A two-level resource partitioning framework.

done on the RRP Model, e.g., [5] and [6], which theoretically introduce how partitions in RRP are defined by the parameters **Availability Factor** and **Supply Regularity**. Better scheduling algorithms based on RRP are also proposed for single core [6] and multi-core scenarios [11], which greatly increase the utilization of the physical resources. Li and Cheng [7] also prove that uniprocessor scheduling algorithms can be directly reused for task scheduling on a single partition.

However, as stated before, a virtual machine may contain several partitions, each with different computational power. How to schedule tasks on different partitions has received little attention. This paper proposes a centralized task-partition architecture connecting the resource level and the task level based on the RRP Model. Usage of Shared Memory segment (SM) to map tasks to partitions, also enables transparency between the two levels by maintaining code level independence.

Based on this architecture, we correlate the model of mapping periodic tasks to regular partitions to the model of online Multiple Knapsack Problem (MKP), which further enables us to develop the Regular-Partition Periodic Task Mapping (RPM) Model. Considering that RPM only takes periodic tasks into count, which is not quite realistic, we further propose the Regular-Partition Compositional Task Mapping (RCM) Model to map both sporadic and periodic tasks to regular partitions.

Being the first ever attempt to map a task to a partition based on RRP Model, this paper borrows certain ideas from different variants of online MKP [12]. Though the work is still under progress, We have already proved that a simple strategy Best Fit can reach a constant competitive ratio of $\frac{1}{2}$ for RPM under certain type of inputs. This paper introduces the architecture

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in Section II and the two models, together with the evaluation of them in Section III.

II. CENTRALIZED TASK-PARTITION ARCHITECTURE

The bridge between the resource level and the task level becomes increasingly vital as there is a pressing need for partitions in resource level to accommodate the incoming task requests. In this section, we first introduce how the allocation of tasks to partitions are done. Then we discuss the method of implementing the architecture.

A. Task Manager (TM)

TM is a platform where tasks are uploaded and mapped as shown in Fig. 2. All tasks shall upload their information (Worst Case Execution times, Arrival times, Relative deadlines and etc.) in **upload()** to TM. TM then queues up all the requests in a large queue(s) and performs mapping (**map()**) on each available task request in the queue one by one. Discussion concerning the size of the queue will be presented in the future work. The function **map()** maps the incoming task to a suitable partition. It also updates the partition information when the previous task is mapped to a partition so that the current task request is well aware of the changes at the partition level. Post mapping, the task requests are dispatched (**dispatch()**) to their assigned partitions through shared memory segment model. Hence, after mapping, the task request shall have a new field appended to the request i.e., Partition ID along with the existing task information.

How the mapping is performed in **map()** is discussed in Section III. Next discuss the efficiency of the mechanism.

B. The advantages of TM

Due to the real-time constraints, tasks are supposed to be mapped to a certain partition when they arrive. Adopting a TM reduces the number of communication channels needed for communication. Besides, since partitions are set when the system boots, the shared memory between TM and partitions can also be built in advance and initial information of partitions can be stored in TM at the very beginning. By doing so, the time taken to map a task to its assigned partition can be significantly reduced. Next, we discuss the efficiency of deploying the shared memory segment.

C. Shared Memory Segment (SM)

The dispatching of task request to the assigned partition post mapping can thus be implemented either using the concept of pipes or Shared Memory (SM). However, pipe is limited to the communication between two processes with the same parent process. Hence, SM suits the scenarios where processes are independent from one another better. Also, as the message packet that has to be sent across is quite large in size, usage of SM can be beneficial and efficient at the same time. The **dispatch()** using SM shall be dealt in detail in the future work.

III. REGULAR-PARTITION TASK MAPPING MODELS

In this section, we consider how to map periodic tasks and sporadic tasks to a set of regular partitions. To begin with, we briefly review the RRP Model first.

Fig. 2. Centralized Task-Partition Architecture .

A. A Brief Review in RRP Model

The RRP Model divides physical resources into different partitions. Each partition P_i is characterized by the availability factor α_i and the supply regularity k_i . α_i is the ratio of time units P_i takes during a hyper period in a physical resource. Suppose a partition occupies a CPU core, then its availability factor would be 1. The availability factor is always less than or equal to 1 [6].

Let $S_i(t)$ denote the time units P_i takes before time t . Then we can define the instant regularity [6] to be $Ir_i(t) = S(t) - t\alpha_i$. Accordingly, we can define the supply regularity k_i .

$$k_i = \lceil \max Ir_i(t) - \min Ir_i(t) \rceil \quad (1)$$

With Equation 1, we can see the supply regularity, which is an integer no smaller than 1, bounds the deviation between the ideal and the actual resource allocation. Depending on the value of k_i , P_i can be a **regular partition** ($k_i = 1$) or an **irregular partition** ($k_i > 1$).

Here we present the characteristic that only regular partitions possess, with the following theorem.

Theorem 1: A regular partition P_i can guarantee that it owns at least one time unit every $\frac{1}{\alpha_i}$ time units.

Theorem 1 indicates regular partitions can be well utilized and predicted with merely the availability factors and the supply regularities. Further details supporting theorem 1 shall be dealt in detail in future work. In next subsection, we will show how the characteristics shown in theorem 1 can be utilized to simplify the mapping problem.

B. Regular-Partition Periodic Task Mapping (RPM)

In this subsection, we consider how to map periodic tasks to regular partitions. To accomplish the goal, we first show how to perform the schedulability test for a task set on a partition with merely partition's availability factor and supply regularity.

To judge whether mapping a periodic task to a regular partition is schedulable or not, having knowledge of the partition's availability factor and supply regularity is sufficient. We first define a periodic task set T , element j in which $T_j = (c_j, d_j, p_j, R_j)$ where c_j stands for Worst Case Execution Time (WCET), d_j for the relative deadline, p_j for the period and R_j for arrival time of T_j . No information about T_j shall be known before it arrives.

Theorem 2: A task set T is schedulable on a regular partition P_i iff

$$\sum_{j=1}^{|T|} \frac{c_j}{\min\{d_j, p_j\}} \leq \alpha_i \quad (2)$$

The Proof of Theorem 2 will be given in the future work. With Theorem 2, we can reduce the problem of mapping periodic tasks to regular partitions into an online MKP.

First, we review the definition of an online MKP problem. Each item is defined by its size, value and arrival time while each bin is defined by its capacity. The sum of the sizes of the items placed in a certain bin cannot exceed the capacity of the bin. When an item is successfully placed, we gain its value as a reward. The goal is to maximize the values gained [12].

Here, partition is a bin, whose capacity is its availability factor while a periodic task T_j is an item with a size of $\frac{c_j}{\min\{d_j, p_j\}}$. As for the value of T_j , we have two different assumptions. If we assume each task to be equally important to the system, values obtained on putting any task into a bin remain the same, i.e., 1. With this assumption, the mapping problem is thus reduced to the **unit case** of online MKP [12]. On the other hand, if our primary goal is to maximize the utilization ratio of physical resources, we set the value of a task to be the same as its size $\frac{c_j}{\min\{d_j, p_j\}}$. Such an assumption corresponds to the **proportional case** of online MKP [12]. Besides, in this online mapping problem, without knowledge of the future, the system will not abandon a task actively unless there is no space for the task. This resembles the setting of the Fair Bin variant of online MKP [13].

This is the RPM model derived from online MKP. Algorithms for the two variants of the RPM Model and the analysis of these algorithms will be presented in the future work.

C. Regular-Partition Compositional Task Mapping

In last subsection, the absence of sporadic tasks in the task set brings in decent simplification to the model. However, RPM is not realistic enough as sporadic tasks are important in real-time systems. In this subsection, we attempt to formulate a new model Regular-Partition Compositional Task Mapping (RCM), with both periodic and sporadic tasks considered.

Unlike periodic tasks, sporadic tasks are not that predictable. Therefore, we regard sporadic tasks as single-instance tasks in our model since it is not worthy to hold the resources for the next instance that may not come in the near future. Once an instance of the sporadic tasks is generated, it will be uploaded to the task manager and mapped to a partition in run time. This instance leaves the system when it is done without occupying any resources further.

Hence, we redefine the compositional task set T so that both sporadic and periodic tasks can be accommodated into the model. Task T_j in T is defined by $T_j = (c_j, d_j, p_j, R_j, D_j)$. Similarly, c_j is the WCET and d_j is the relative deadline while p_j is the period. R_j is the arrival time and D_j is the leaving time. To be specific, after D_j , no execution on T_j is needed. For periodic tasks that do not leave the system, D_j is $+\infty$. For

sporadic tasks, regarded as single-instance tasks, they always have: $d_j = p_j$ and $D_j = R_j + d_j$.

Fortunately, the schedulability test shown in Equation 2 is still valid for the compositional task set. Therefore, model RCM is exactly the same as model RPM except that task T_j will leave the system after D_j . RCM problem is more realistic yet harder to solve as well.

D. Evaluation of RPM and RCM

Closer to the traditional online MKP, RPM is a problem easier to solve since it does not involve the leaving of tasks. So far, we already prove that a simple strategy Best Fit can reach a constant competitive ratio of $\frac{1}{2}$ in RPM.

Though RCM is harder to solve, the fact that it shares most of the features with RPM makes it less challenging. For instance, the reason why Best Fit performs well is that it gathers the spare space for the unknown future, which is also valid and a necessity in solving RCM. Based on these features, we develop another algorithm considering not only the capacity but also tasks' leaving time, while allocating tasks. More details and contributions will be given in the future work.

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